

VISCOSE FIBRE REINFORCED HIGH-DENSITY POLYETHYLENE AS A FOOD CONTACT MATERIAL

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Abstract: *In recent years, biocomposites have gained increasing attention in both industry and academia as a promising sustainable alternative to conventional composites. While the application range of biocomposites is continuously increasing, they are still very little used as food contact materials. The aim of the present study was to investigate the suitability of viscose fibres as reinforcement in thermoplastic biocomposites intended for food contact applications. Viscose fibres were compounded into biobased high-density polyethylene (HDPE) using a co-rotating twin-screw extruder and test specimens were injection moulded. Biocomposites were prepared using untreated and pelletized viscose fibres and the effect of the addition of compatibilizer and lubricant was investigated. Morphological, mechanical, rheological and migration properties of the prepared samples were characterised. Untreated fibres exhibited a significantly higher reinforcing effect than pelletized fibres due to better dispersion. The addition of a compatibilizer resulted in enhanced interfacial adhesion and fibre dispersion, which was reflected in increased tensile strength. The overall migration of all studied compositions was well below the permitted level, while the addition of a compatibilizer resulted in a strong acidic flavour in sensory tests, which is not permissible in food contact applications. The results showed that viscose fibres are a promising candidate for the preparation of thermoplastic biocomposites for food contact applications.*

Keywords: biocomposites, viscose fibres, high-density polyethylene, food contact materials, overall migrations

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymeric materials are often used in food contact applications, where low migrations to food is an essential requirement. European Commission regulation (EC) 10/2011 specifies the requirements for plastic products intended for food contact, such as a list of authorized monomers and additives and migration limits (European Commission, 2011). In recent years, biocomposites, such as natural fibre (NF) or man-made cellulose fibre (MMCF) reinforced polymers, gained increased attention as a promising sustainable alternative to conventional composites (Gurunathan, Mohanty and Nayak, 2015; Pickering, Efendy and Le, 2016a). However, their application as food contact materials is rarely explored in the scientific literature (Berthet *et al.*, 2016). NF or MMCF possess many attractive properties, such as high specific strength and modulus, high abundance, renewability, and biodegradability (Gurunathan, Mohanty and Nayak, 2015). MMCF, such as viscose fibres, offers additional benefits as they are produced under controlled conditions, resulting in uniform and homogeneous structures and high chemical purity, which may be especially advantageous in the case of food contact applications (Bulota *et al.*, 2020). However, the preparation of cellulose fibre (CF) reinforced polymer composites presents many challenges, namely, problems with fibre feeding, low thermal stability and poor interactions with the polymer matrix. CF are difficult to process using conventional melt mixing equipment due to low bulk density that causes problems with the feeding of fibres. Compacting the fibres into pellets using pelletizing process has proven to be a suitable technique to overcome this challenge, but it also comes with its drawbacks as fibre pellets are harder to disperse in a polymer matrix and pelletizing can lead to the shortening of fibres. The addition of lubricants to fibres before the pelletizing process can decrease the aforementioned negative effects associated with fibre pelletizing (Jacobson *et al.*, 2001; Hietala and Oksman, 2018). CF are not well thermally stable and can start to degrade during melt blending with polymers which leads to the formation of low molecular products (Yang and Kokot, 1996; Feldmann, 2016). In the case of food contact applications, these degradation products may unwantedly migrate into foods (European Commission, 2011; Berthet *et al.*, 2016). As CF are hydrophilic in nature, they exhibit poor interactions with hydrophobic polymers, which leads to poor mechanical properties of the composites. Usually, compatibilizers are added to CF composites to improve the interaction between the interfaces, resulting in higher mechanical performance (Gurunathan, Mohanty and Nayak, 2015; Pickering, Efendy and Le, 2016b).

Having outlined challenges in mind, the present study aimed to evaluate the suitability of viscose fibres as a reinforcing agent for HDPE intended for food contact applications. Composites were prepared by extrusion directly from fibres and from fibre pellets to evaluate how pelletizing process influences the mechanical and migration properties of the composites. The effect of the addition of lubricant before the pelletizing process and the addition of compatibilizer was also studied.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Biobased HDPE (SHA 7260) was a product of Braskem (Brazil). Viscose fibres (Danufil Viscose Type KS GL) were kindly by Kelheim Fibres (Germany). The viscose fibres had a linear density of 1.7 dTex and a cutting length of 5 mm. Lubricant (Crodamide ER) was a product of Croda Lubricants and is chemically an erucamide. Compatibilizer (HDPE grafted with maleic anhydride (HDPE-g-MA)) (Graftabond HD-MAH 02030 C) was kindly provided by Graft Polymer (Slovenia). According to the manufacturer, HDPE-g-MA had a grafting degree of 2.5 % - 3.0 % and MFI of 17 g/10 min to 23 g/10 min (190 °C / 2.16 kg).

2.2 Sample preparation

2.2.1 Pelletizing

The fibres were pelletized on Techno Aspira PTA 50 pelletizer. The pelletizer had a 4 kW electric motor and a 6 mm die plate. Prior to pelletizing the fibres were conditioned to a moisture content of 20 wt. %. The lubricant was to the fibres before the pelletizing by dry mixing.

2.2.2 Compounding

The viscose fibres were dried prior to processing in a laboratory oven at 105 °C to the moisture content below 0.1 wt.%. Composites were prepared on a co-rotating twin-screw extruder (LabTech LTE 20-44). The extruder had an L:D ratio of 44:1 and a screw size of 20 mm. The screw speed was 300 min⁻¹ and the barrel temperature was 170 °C. The composition of samples is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Composition of samples

Sample	HDPE (%)	Fibres (%)	Pellets (%)	HDPE-g-MA (%)	Lubricant (%)
HDPE	100	/	/	/	/
CF	80	20	/	/	/
CP	80	/	20	/	/
CP-L	79.6	/	20	/	0.4
CF-C	79	20	/	1	/
CP-LC	78.6	/	20	1	0.4

2. 2. 3 Injection moulding

Test specimens (according to ISO 527 1BA and ISO 179) were prepared on an injection moulding machine (Krauss Maffei CX 180-50). The injection moulding machine had a clamping force of 500 kN and a screw size of 30 mm. The barrel temperature was 170 °C, mould temperature was 20 °C, injection speed was 80 mm/s, packing pressure was 90 MPa for 8 seconds, back pressure was 5.0 MPa, screw speed was 150 min⁻¹ and cooling time was 8 seconds.

2. 3 Characterization

2. 3. 1 Fibre dispersion

The fibre dispersion was evaluated by optical analysis of compression moulded films produced from injection moulded specimens. The tensile test specimen was pressed on a Baopin BP-8170-B hydraulic press at 200 °C, first using a pressure of 0.3 MPa for 60 seconds, then using a pressure of 3.0 MPa for 20 seconds. The prepared films were scanned using Konica Minolta Bizhub C250i scanner in greyscale mode, using 300 dpi resolution.

2. 3. 2 Tensile tests

Tensile properties were determined on a universal testing machine (Shimadzu Ag-X plus 10 kN) according to ISO 527 standard. The test speed was set to 1 mm/s (up to 0.25 % strain) and to 50 mm/s (from 0.25 % strain to break).

2. 3. 3 Charpy impact tests

The Charpy impact strength was determined using a pendulum impact tester (LIYI LY-XJJD5) according to ISO 179 standard. The samples were tested using a 4 J hammer.

2.3.4 Melt flow index

The melt flow index (MFI) was determined using a melt flow index analyser (LIYI LY-RR) according to ISO 1133 standard. The samples were measured at 190 °C using a 2.16 kg weight.

2.3.5 Migration tests and sensory analysis

Total overall migrations (TOM) of samples were determined using two different liquid food simulants: ethanol 10 % (v/v) (simulant A) and acetic acid 3 % (m/v) (simulant B). The tensile test specimens of a total surface area of 1 dm² were immersed into a beaker containing 100 ml of food simulant. The extraction was done in a laboratory oven at 70 °C for two hours. After the incubation period, the samples were removed, and the simulants were evaporated at 105 °C. The residue was weighed using an analytical balance with a precision of 1 mg. The overall migrations were determined according to the following equation:

$$M = \frac{m \times a_2 \times 1000}{q \times a_1}$$

Where M was total overall migration (mg/kg), m was a mass (mg) of extraction residual, a_2 was a surface area (dm²) of a final product, q was a mass (g) of food in contact with the material, a_1 was a surface area (dm²) of the tested specimens.

The indicative tests of sensory analysis were performed under conditions described in DIN 10955 standard. Samples with a total surface area of 1 dm² were boiled in a beaker filled with 100 ml of overboiled drinking water at 100 °C for 30 minutes. After the incubation period, the samples were removed from the beaker, the solution was cooled to room temperature, and the sensory analysis of odour and taste of unlabelled samples was performed by two testers. The odour and taste were empirically evaluated by scoring the intensity according to the scale where value 0 presents no detectable odour or flavour and value 4 presents very strong odour and flavour.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fibre dispersion

Figure 1 presents images of compression moulded tensile test specimens of different samples. The visible white spots were ascribed to viscose fibre agglomerates. In general, composites prepared directly from fibres (Figure 1 a, d) had large agglomerates distributed across the film, with some parts of the

film having larger and thicker agglomerates, visible as bright white spots. Some agglomerates were considerably less intense that seemed just as a network of entangled fibres. On the other hand, composites prepared from pellets (Figure 1 b, c, e) had agglomerates in form of small round shaped spots. These spots seemed much more compacted as agglomerates prepared directly from fibres. When HDPE-g-MA was added to the composite prepared directly from fibres the films exhibited considerably fewer agglomerates, especially those visible with intense white colour. This effect was ascribed to improved interaction between the fibre and the matrix that allowed better distribution of the fibres. Composites prepared from pellets with added lubricant had agglomerates that were larger in size and more resembling agglomerates of composites prepared directly from fibres. Nevertheless, composites still had a high number of small agglomerates that were looking the same as those of composites prepared directly from pellets.

Figure 1: Scanned films of compression moulded specimens of samples: (a) CF; (b) CP; (c) CP-L; (d) CF-C; (e) CP-LC.

3. 2 Tensile test

The addition of cellulose pellets into HDPE increased tensile modulus (E_t) approximately by a factor of 3, while the addition of untreated fibres increased E_t by a factor of 4 (Figure 2a). Tensile strength (σ_m) was significantly increased by the addition of untreated fibres (+ 40 %), while the addition of pellets only slightly increased σ_m (+ 4 %) (Figure 1b). These differences were ascribed to better dispersion of untreated fibres as discussed in chapter 3. 1. Furthermore,

pelletizing process could shorten the fibres due to mechanical forces, which also reflects in decreased strength of the composites (Hietala and Oksman, 2018). The addition of lubricant to the pellets resulted in a higher increase of σ_m (+ 11 %), which can be explained by enhanced dispersion or less damage to the fibres due to the presence of lubricant (Hietala and Oksman, 2018). The addition of HDPE-g-MA to the composites prepared directly from fibres resulted in the highest value of σ_m (+ 73 %), while HDPE-g-MA had only a slight effect on σ_m when added to the composites prepared from lubricated pellets. HDPE-g-MA reacts with the hydroxyl group of the cellulose fibre, thus decreases the polarity of the fibre surface, which in turn results in better wettability of the fibres and stronger interfacial adhesion between the fibre and the matrix, leading to increased σ_m . However, HDPE-g-MA can also react with the amine group of the lubricant, thus diminishing its positive effects on σ_m . Strain at break (ϵ_b) decreased from 534 % for neat HDPE to the values in the range of 6 % - 10 % for composites (Figure 2c). Here, the opposites trends were found, where composites with higher value of σ_m exhibited lower values of ϵ_b , with the exception of sample CP-LC.

Figure 2: Tensile properties of samples: (a) tensile modulus; (b) tensile strength; (c) strain at break.

3. 3 Charpy impact strength

Unnotched Charpy impact strength (a_{cU}) of samples is presented in Figure 3. Specimens of neat HDPE did not break during the Charpy test. Both composites prepared directly from fibres exhibited a_{cU} values around 20 kJ/m², while composites prepared from pellets exhibited a_{cU} values around 25 kJ/m². Composites prepared directly from fibres exhibited better fibre dispersion and thus more fibre ends, that act as a weak point where crack initiation occurs which leads to premature failure.

Figure 3: Unnotched Charpy impact strength of samples

3. 4 Melt flow index

MFI results of samples are presented in Figure 4. HDPE had an MFI of 17.1 g / 10 min, while composites exhibited significantly lower MFI, which ranged from 0.4 g/10 min to 4.1 g/10 min. MFI results correlate well to the mechanical properties of the composites, although here the differences between the samples are even more evident. Composites prepared from untreated fibres (sample CF) exhibited lower MFI values compared to composites prepared from pellets (sample CP) by a factor of 4 that was ascribed to better dispersion of viscose fibres that results in higher viscosity. The addition of lubricant to the pellets resulted in a 2-fold decrease in MFI value, even though low molecular weight lubricants, usually promotes the flow behaviour of polymeric materials. The addition of HDPE-g-MA to the composites prepared directly from pellets decreased MFI by 3-fold, while it slightly increased the MFI of composites prepared from pellets.

Figure 4: Melt flow index of samples

3. 5 Migration tests and sensory analysis

TOM of samples in ethanol and acetic acid are presented in Figure 5a. TOM of all samples in both ethanol and acetic acid were up to around 22 mg/kg, which is significantly lower than the allowed TOM limit of 60 mg/kg. In general, higher TOM values were measured in ethanol, except for sample CP, which also exhibited 2- to 3-fold higher TOM in ethanol compared to other samples. Higher TOM in ethanol of sample CP may be due to degradation products that formed during the unlubricated pelletizing process, as these pellets were slightly yellowish in colour. Results of the sensory analysis are presented in Figure 5b. According to DIN 10955 standard, the product is suitable for food contact use if the solution obtained by boiling of sample exhibits only a weak odour and flavour (up to a value of 2). Solution of HDPE exhibited just barely detectable flavour and odour. Solutions of composites without HDPE-g-MA exhibited no detectable odour, whereas the flavour of these solutions differed. Solution of sample CF had no detectable flavour, while both sample CP and CP-L had a slight flavour that may arise due to degradation products formed during pelletizing and/or due to lubricant content. On the other hand, both composites with added HDPE-g-MA exhibited noticeable odour and strong acidic flavour that was ascribed to the presence of unreacted maleic anhydride. Migration tests sensory analysis results indicate that all tested composites without HDPE-g-MA may be suitable for food contact applications.

Figure 5: Results of migration test and sensory analysis: (a) total overall migrations; (b) intensity of flavour and odour

4 CONCLUSIONS

Results of the present study indicate that viscose fibres are a promising biobased and biodegradable reinforcing agent for polymeric materials intended for food contact applications. Composites prepared directly from viscose fibres offer significantly better mechanical performance than composites prepared from pelletized fibres under tested conditions, which could be further improved with the addition of a compatibilizer. However, the processing of former composites has proven to be challenging. TOM of all tested composites was well below the permitted limit, while sensory analysis showed that composites with added compatibilizer are not suitable for food contact applications.

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5 REFERENCES

- Berthet, M. A. et al. (2016). Vegetal fiber-based biocomposites: Which stakes for food packaging applications?, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 133(2). doi: 10.1002/app.42528.
- Bulota, M. et al. (2020). The fiber-matrix interface in Ioncell cellulose fiber composites and its implications for the mechanical performance, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, (July), pp. 1–8. doi: 10.1002/app.50306.

European Commission (2011). Commission Regulation (EU) No 10/2011, Official Journal of the European Union. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2011:012:0001:0089:EN:PDF>.

Feldmann, M. (2016). The effects of the injection moulding temperature on the mechanical properties and morphology of polypropylene man-made cellulose fibre composites, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. Elsevier Ltd, 87, pp. 146–152. doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2016.04.022.

Gurunathan, T., Mohanty, S. and Nayak, S. K. (2015). A review of the recent developments in biocomposites based on natural fibres and their application perspectives, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. Elsevier Ltd, 77, pp. 1–25. doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.06.007.

Hietala, M. and Oksman, K. (2018). Pelletized cellulose fibres used in twin-screw extrusion for biocomposite manufacturing: Fibre breakage and dispersion, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 109(4), pp. 538–545. doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2018.04.006.

Jacobson, R. et al. (2001). Low Temperature Processing of Ultra-Pure Cellulose Fibers into Nylon 6 and Other Thermoplastics, *The Sixth International Conference on Woodfiber-Plastic Composites*, pp. 127–133. Available at: <https://www.fpl.fs.fed.us/documnts/pdf2002/jacob02a.pdf>.

Pickering, K. L., Efendy, M. G. A. and Le, T. M. (2016a). A review of recent developments in natural fibre composites and their mechanical performance, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 83, pp. 98–112. doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.08.038.

Pickering, K. L., Efendy, M. G. A. and Le, T. M. (2016b). A review of recent developments in natural fibre composites and their mechanical performance, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 83, pp. 98–112. doi: 10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.08.038.

Yang, P. and Kokot, S. (1996). Thermal analysis of different cellulosic fabrics, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 60(8), pp. 1137–1146. doi: 10.1002/(SICI)1097-4628(19960523)60:8<1137::AID-APP6>3.0.CO;2-M.